

Data and Code Summary for Extreme AOD Study in USA

Abstract. This document summarizes the data and code used in the study of “Long-term trends of extreme aerosol optical depth events and radiation in North America using multiple satellite retrievals, CERES and MERRA2”. All data are in the [netCDF](#) format and all code to process the data and make plots are written in the NCAR Command Language ([NCL](#)) scripts. The original data and code are located on the [Big Red II](#) high-performance parallel computing system at Indian University.

1. Data

Multiple data sets are used in this study. All data are summarized in Table 1 and can be downloaded freely.

Table 1. Summary of data sets.

Data set	Period	Resolutions		Download link
		Temporal	Spatial (longitude×latitude)	
MERRA2	2000.03–2018.02	Monthly and daily	0.625°×0.5°	https://disc.gsfc.nasa.gov/daac-bin/FTPSubset2.pl
MISR	2000.03–2018.02	Monthly	0.5°×0.5°	ftp://l5ftl01.larc.nasa.gov/MISR/
MODIS-Terra	2000.03–2018.02	Monthly	1°×1°	https://ladsweb.modaps.eosdis.nasa.gov/archive/allData/ https://lpdaac.usgs.gov/dataset_discovery/modis/modis_products_table
	2000.03–2018.02	Monthly and daily	0.05°×0.05°	
MODIS-Aqua	2003.03–2018.02	Monthly	1°×1°	
CERES	2000.03–2018.02	Monthly	1°×1°	https://ceres.larc.nasa.gov/order_data.php
TRMM	2000.03–2018.02	Monthly and daily	0.25°×0.25°	https://mirador.gsfc.nasa.gov/cgi-bin/mirador/presentNavigation.pl?project=TRMM&tree=project

The data are divided into 2 groups: observational and MERRA2. The former is located at [/N/dc2/projects/DoE_WRF/qj1/data/](#) and the latter is mainly located at [/N/dc2/projects/DoE_WRF/MERRA2/](#). Sections 1.1 and 1.2 summarize the locations of the original downloaded data, while Section 2 describes the NCL scripts used to make the 12 figures and the associated processed data, such as annual and seasonal means, temporal trends, area-averaged values of variables.

1.1 Satellite and other observational data

The observational data mainly include multiple satellite data sets: TRMM, MISR, MODIS-Aqua, MODIS-Terra, and CERES. The monthly MERRA2 AOD data are also located here. Most of the data sets are monthly except data sets of TRMM daily precipitation and MODIS-Terra daily surface temperature. These downloaded and pre-processed data are used to derive long-term trends and climatological means using the NCL scripts described in Section 2.

1.2 MERRA2

The MERRA2 data used in this study can be divided into three sub-groups: AOD, radiation, and other meteorological variables. Daily aerosol data include total AOD and AOD of various aerosol compositions. Radiation data covers downwelling, upwelling, and net radiation at the top of atmosphere, in the atmosphere, and at the surface. The other important variables include surface temperature, precipitation, cloud area fraction, and so on.

2. Scripts

There are 10 figures in the main text. The NCL scripts and post-processed data used to create each of the figures are summarized in the above diagram. There are five sub-directories under the main directory of the project, each of which is associated with a sub-topic. For example, “02_aod_clim” contains NCL scripts and data to create figures of climatological AOD spatial patterns and temporal time series.

The data used to make plots are produced by NCL scripts that have the same name with data files except that the data and scripts have different suffixes, such as “.nc” and “.ncl”.

Notes. There are some user-defined NCL functions in “`$NCL/mylib/myfct.ncl`” to make the NCL scripts easier to read. These functions are also included in the compressed file. Without proper loading of these functions, some of these NCL scripts may not be executed successfully. Use this line to load these functions: `load "~/usr/ncl-6.4.0/mylib/myfct.ncl"` at the beginning of each script.

